

Research Article

A Comparison of the Reliability of Six Evapotranspiration Computing Models for Abeokuta in South Western Nigeria

***Egwuonwu C.C., Okafor V.C., Ezeanya N.C., Nzediegwu C. and Okorafor O.O.**

Department of Agricultural Engineering Federal University of Technology, Owerri. Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's Email: nnamdichuks2002@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The Penman modified, Priestly Taylor, Blaney Morin Nigeria, Jensen-Haise, Hargreaves-Samani: and Thornthwaite methods were used to estimate Reference Evapotranspiration (RET) in Abeokuta, Ogun State Nigeria. The Penman modified method was selected as the standard of comparison for evaluating the other five methods. Good correlation was found between the RET values, estimated by each of the five radiation and temperature base and the Penman modified method, although there were some differences.

The methods that performed best in estimating Penman modified RET values at the station were recommended based on the statistical analysis. The reliability of the radiation methods was evaluated when data from Ijebu-Ode station was used to evaluate RET for Abeokuta Station. The Penman modified estimates were used to develop correction factors for their potential use in the temperature-based Thomthwaite and Hargreaves-Samani methods.

Keywords: Comparison, reliability, evapotranspiration, computing models, Abeokuta, South-western Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Evapotranspiration has a controlling influence on hydrological and meteorological processes. In spite of the efforts of several scientists, reliable estimates of regional evapotranspiration are extremely difficult to obtain due probably to the complexity brought about by its dependence on soil condition and plant physiology. Because of this complexity, the concept of reference evapotranspiration (RET) has been introduced, which no longer depends so critically on soil and plant factors but has been shown to primarily depend on climatic factors. There are several paradoxical interactions which complicates research on an accurate modeling of evapotranspiration. Several methods of estimating RET are presently in use perhaps with the assumption that errors if any, will be damped out upon averaging in space and time domains. Judging the accuracy of the available methods is not easy. Even experimentally observed data have limitations due to the difficulties of simulating the ideal conditions as defined for RET.

Therefore, the physical and dynamical nature of this formula has to be taken as a guideline in evaluating the relative merits of the formula.

The concept of RET is useful to make its measurement worthwhile. Skaggs et al. (1995) provides a list of such uses of the concept of RET. One of the most important uses of the concept has been in the calculation of crop water requirements. This has been made the basis of a number of successful schemes of irrigation control. The basis of these schemes and many other of its type is the mutual dependence of both RET and photosynthesis on the radioactive energy flux from the sun.

Another climatologically importance of the concept of RET includes the assessment of water surplus and water deficit among many other components of the water balance. When the soil is at field capacity, actual evapotranspiration (AE) will equal evapotranspiration at potential rate and moisture input exceeds RET. The excess rainfall over evapotranspiration is referred to as water surplus (Egwuonwu, 2011).

Conversely, water deficit is referred to as the excess of RET over rainfall. Using the value of RET obtained by the Penman's method together with rainfall values for stations in West Africa, estimates were made for water surplus or water deficit for the region. One other important communication application of the concept of RET is in the classification of climatic regions. The main purpose of the research reported in this paper was to evaluate the reliability of the five approximate RET prediction methods as compared to the standard Penman modified (PM)

method using data collected in Abeokuta in South-western Nigeria. The mean monthly and annual RET values estimated by the five methods were compared with estimates by the standard PM method. The objective for such comparison is to examine the relationships and to determine the method that best predicted RET as compared to the PM method. The second objective was to evaluate the reliability of the methods when data from nearby stations are used for estimating RET. Thirdly, monthly correction factors for adjusting the Hargreaves and Thornthwaite methods were developed for their potential use at the study site.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Six different methods (one combination: Penman Modified; two radiation based: Priestly Taylor and Jensen Haise and three temperature based: Hargreaves, Samani, Thornthwaite and Blaney-Morin Nigeria) were used to estimate RET in Abeokuta, Meteorological data were collected from meteorological stations distributed all over the study area for the period of 1985-2004 with the assistance of the computer unit of the Federal Meteorological Center Oshodi, Lagos. The weather parameters collected are mean monthly values of air temperature including maximum and minimum temperatures, sunshine hours, wind speed, vapour pressure, relative humidity and rainfall. The short-wave radiation (R_n), possible sunshine duration (N), black body radiation (TK^4), rate of change of temperature with saturation vapour pressure (A), Psychrometric coefficient (γ), mean atmospheric pressure as a function of attitude (P) were all obtained from meteorological tables.

The mean monthly RET was computed for each month using weather data for that month in the RET equation.

Regressions analysis were performed to examine the relationships of the mean monthly RET estimates from the five methods with the mean monthly estimates by the standard Penman modified method. The regression equations computed was in the form

$$Y = mX + c \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where Y represents Penman modified mean monthly RET, X is the mean monthly RET estimated from each of the other five methods, m and c are slope and intercept respectively.

The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) parameter was used to indicate the goodness of the fit of RET estimates as compared to the standard PM method without any adjustment. Other parameters used include the slope of the regression (m), the intercept (c) and the correlation coefficient (r). The best method is the one with the c value closest to zero, m value closest to 1.0, the highest r and the smallest RMSE (Parmele and McGuinness 1974). Abtew (1996) and Parmele and McGuinness (1974) used standard error and other statistical parameters for the evaluation of RET models. Pindyck and Rubinfeld (1981) stated that "when the goal of a model is to maximize the precision of the predictions (the objective assumed), for example, an estimator with very low variance and some bias, may be more desirable than an unbiased estimator with high variance. The useful criterion in this regard is the goal of minimizing RMSE".

The conclusions were further verified by calculating a t-statistics for each of these models as was suggested by Jacovides and Kontaytinanis (1995). These authors suggested that the t-statistic should be used in conjunction with the RMSE to better evaluate a model's performance.

Data from Ijebu-Ode station were applied to compute radiation for estimating the RET in Abeokuta. Solar radiation (R_s) was first computed for Ijebu-Ode station using the relation.

$$R_s = R_A (0.5n/N + 0.25) \dots \dots \dots (2).$$

Similarly, net radiation (R_n) was calculated by the following empirical relationship (Jensen et al.. 1990).

$$R_n = R_s (1-\alpha) - [(0.9n/N + 0.1)(0.34 - \sqrt{0.139e_d})]TK^4 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The net radiation calculated using this method was calibrated with observed net radiation in Abeokuta station. Predictions by these methods, using empirically calculated radiation data were compared to prediction by the PM method using actual data. This allowed an evaluation of the reliability of these methods when on site radiation data were not available and data from the nearest station was used. Mean monthly correction factors for the Hargreaves-Samani and Thornthwaite methods were computed as the ratio of the total monthly Penman modified RET to the monthly total for each method averaged over the record period for the station.

Table 1: Long Term (1985-2004) Mean Monthly Weather Parameters for Abeokuta Station.

Month	J	F	M	A	M	J	JY	A	S	O	N	D
Max. Tem (°C)	34.3	32.2	35.5	34.3	32.7	30.9	29.9	29.0	30.0	31.6	33.4	33.8
Min. Tem (°C)	21.9	24.1	24.8	24.3	23.8	22.7	22.6	22.5	22.5	22.8	23.2	22.3
Air Tem (°C)	22.7	29.2	29.1	28.5	27.4	25.8	25.5	25.4	27.7	26.7	27.9	27.3
V. Pressure (mb)	23.2	28.1	30.6	31.6	31.0	29.7	28.2	27.8	28.5	29.7	29.9	26.1
Wind Speed	1.9	2.1	2.0	1.7	2.0	1.9	1.8	1.8	2.2	1.8	1.9	2.0
Length of Sunshine	11.7	11.9	12.1	12.3	12.5	12.6	12.5	12.4	12.2	12.0	11.8	11.7
Actual Sunshine	3.7	5.2	5.2	5.5	5.5	3.9	2.6	2.4	3.1	4.6	5.2	4.6
Relative Humidity (%)	65	68	74	81	81	83	87	88	86	85	78	72
Rainfall (mm)	5.9	31.2	69.2	113.3	142.5	192.9	155.1	88.3	185.7	110.2	15.8	19.0
R _a	13.7	14.6	15.4	15.5	15.2	14.9	15.0	15.3	15.3	14.9	14.9	13.4
R _a	2.90	4.32	3.97	4.54	4.36	3.54	2.95	2.94	3.29	3.89	3.94	3.29

Table 2 Mean Monthly and Annual RET estimated by different methods for Abeokuta Station

Month	PM	JH	PT	BMN	HS	TH
J	131.2	101.2	86.7	83.6	156.8	158.1
F	132.1	124.0	108.9	109.7	153.8	179.1
M	142.4	136.3	131.1	121.2	168.1	198.9
A	132.3	128.4	132.3	122.5	156.8	180.1
M	128.4	116.3	129.5	123.5	146.1	161.7
J	103.5	81.4	129.5	123.5	146.1	161.7
JY	100.4	66.0	58.6	55.9	125.0	121.5
A	103.7	61.2	85.6	55.9	125.0	121.5
S	106.6	72.5	92.5	64.8	126.1	118.4
O	117.7	100.4	114.6	101.7	140.2	135.6
N	120.4	115.5	113.2	114.3	140.9	158.8
D	121.4	106.3	97.7	103.1	146.5	149.2
Annual	1440.1	1205.5	1276.0	1133.6	1708.5	1804.3

RESULTS

The mean monthly and mean annual RET obtained by averaging the monthly and annual values across the period of record for the station is summarized in Table 2.

At Abeokuta Station, all the methods except Hargreaves-Samani (HS) and Thornthwaites (TH) underestimated the Penman modified (PM) RET which was used as a standard as shown in Table 2. Jensen-Haise (JH), Priestly Taylor (PT) and Blaney Morin Nigeria (BMN) underestimated PM by 16%, 11% and 21% respectively while HS and TH overestimated PM by 19% and 25% respectively. The radiation based methods i.e. JH and PT closely estimated PM Ret in this station. This was partly due to the low wind speed, high air temperature and vapour pressure for the station as well as the areas rocky terrain. On the average, the PT and JH methods were generally the best in estimating the mean annual RET for the station. The TH and HS methods over predicted monthly RET for each month while JH, PT and BMN under predicted the mean monthly for each month.

The summary of statistics for regression of mean monthly RET estimated by each of the five methods against that estimated by the standard Penman modified method is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Statistics for Regression of Mean Monthly RET estimated by five methods against that estimated by Penman Modified RET methods for Abeokuta station.

Method of estimate	Regression	R	RMSE	t-value
JH	$Y = 0.52X + 6775$	0.94	23.12	2.36
PT	$Y = 0.14X + 104.97$	0.18	18.37	2.08
BMN	$Y = 0.44X + 78.72$	0.83	30.12	2.98
HS	$Y = 0.90X + 7.85$	0.98	22.67	3.79
TH	$Y = 0.49X + 46.83$	0.96	33.32	3.68

The best method for estimating RET (as stated in the methodology) compared to Penman modified method is the one with c closest to zero, m closest to 1.0, the smallest RMSE and t statistics values and the highest r with greater emphasis on the RMSE and t values. Based on these results, the Priestly Taylor model ranked first with the lowest RMSE and t value for RET predictions in Abeokuta Station as illustrated in Table 3. Statistic for the Jensen Haise model were nearly as good, making it the second best predictor even though it had a better r, m and c than Priestly Taylor model.

The monthly net radiation obtained by using equation (3) with weather data from Ijebu-Ode station was correlated with the net radiation at Abeokuta Station. The calibration equation obtained was

$$R_n (\text{Abeokuta}) = 0.43R_n (\text{Ijebu Ode}) + 0.40 \dots \dots \dots (4).$$

The reliability of each RET method was tested by using the net radiation obtained by calibration for Abeokuta station using the values for Ijebu Ode station.

The estimates by all five methods using the calibrated radiation data from Ijebu-Ode was compared to the estimates by the Penman modified method using measured data at Abeokuta station as shown in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4: Comparative Statistics of Penman Modified RET prediction by five methods for the period of 1985-2004 At Abeokuta Station using Actual Data from the Station.

	PM	JH	PT	BMN	HS	TH
Total annual RET (mm)	1440.1	1205.5	1276.0	1133.6	1708.5	1804.3
Slope, m		0.52	0.14	0.44	0.90	0.49
c (mm)		67.75	104.97	78.72	-7.85	46.38
R		0.94	0.18	0.83	0.98	0.96
t-value		2.38	2.08	2.98	3.79	3.68
RMSE		23.12	18.37	30.12	22.67	33.32

Table 5: Comparative Statistics of Penman Modified RET Prediction by five methods for the period of 1985-2004 at Abeokuta Station using Empirical Relationship with data for Net Radiation from Ijebu-Ode Station.

	PM	JH	PT	BMN	HS	TH
Total annual RET (mm)	1440.1	1216.2	1281.8	1133.6	1708.5	1804.3
Slope, m		0.49	0.74	0.44	0.90	0.49
c (mm)		70.33	40.74	78.72	-7.85	46.38
R		0.90	0.84	0.83	0.98	0.96
t-value		2.19	2.18	2.98	3.79	3.68
RMSE		23.13	18.37	30.12	22.67	33.32

The RET estimated by all the radiation based methods namely Jensen Haise and Priestly Taylor were comparable to the Penman modified estimates. The degree of fit of the regression on a monthly basis improved, considerably from that achieved with the measured weather data for the same period (Table 5). The Priestly Taylor model again performed better as there was significant improvement in almost all of its statistical parameters compared to other models most especially that of Jensen Haise being radiation based. The reason for the positive results achieved as highlighted above was probably due to a strong correlation of radiation obtained by using empirical relationships with data from the Ijebu-Ode station.

The monthly correction factors for adjusting the Hargreaves-Samani and the Thornthwaites method for their potential use in the station (Abeokuta) is summarized in table 6.

Table 6: Monthly Correction Factors for adjusting Hargeraves-Samani and Thornthwaite RET for Abeokuta Station.

Abeokuta station		
Month	HS	TH
J	0.84	0.83
F	0.86	0.74
M	0.85	0.72
A	0.84	0.73
M	0.88	0.79
J	0.81	0.83
JH	0.80	0.83
A	0.86	0.87
S	0.85	0.90
O	0.84	0.87
N	0.85	0.81
D	0.83	0.81

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were drawn from the results of the study.

1. The mean annual RET estimated by the Standard Penman Modified method for Abeokuta station was found to be 1,440mm.
2. The mean annual RET estimated by the other methods namely Jensen-Haise, Priestly Taylor, Blaney-Morin Nigeria, Hargeaves-Samani and Thornthwaites were found to be 1205.5mm, 1276.0mm, 1133.6mm, 1798.5mm and 1804.3mm respectively.
3. The best RET estimate for Abeokuta station was given by Priestly-Taylor method.
4. The RET estimates obtained using the radiation based methods for a station was highly reliable when data from another station was used. For instance, the annual RET values for Abeokuta station using the radiation based methods with the actual station data were 1205 mm for Jensen Haise and 1276mm for Priestly Taylor. With data from Ijebu-Ode station, the annual RET values for Abeokuta station was 1216mm and 1281.8mm for Jensen-Haise and Priestly Taylor respectively. The values compared favourably well.
5. Monthly correction factors were deduced for Thornthwaite and Hargreave-Samani methods for their potential use at the station in order to give a more accurate estimate as compared to the standard Penman modified.
6. The comparison of methods for estimating RET in different stations is very important since the accurate estimation of ET, hence, crop water requirement is a sine qua non for efficient planning, operation and management of irrigation systems.

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